

Challenges in Implementation of GST in India

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INTRODUCTION

The introduction of the Goods and Services Tax will be a very noteworthy step in the field of indirect tax reforms in India. By merging a large number of Central and State taxes into a single tax, GST is expected to significantly ease double taxation and make taxation overall easy for the industries. For the end customer, the most beneficial will be in terms of reduction in the overall tax burden on goods and services. Introduction of GST will also make Indian products competitive in the domestic and international markets. Once implemented, the proposed taxation system holds great promise in terms of sustaining growth for the Indian economy. The Goods and Services Tax commonly known as GST was introduced in India on 1st July 2017. The basic idea to introduce GST in India to remove the multiple tax system which was a part of central and state government and to provide uniform tax system throughout the country. The present GST tax model is inspired from the Canadian GST model and is divided into different tax slabs ranging from 0% to 28%. After implementation of GST, India became one of the 160 countries to introduce a unified tax regime at midnight. And by unified, we mean four slabs (5%, 12%, 18%, and 28%) and an additional 'sin tax' of 40% to be implemented on rare occasions.

India is facing some of the GST implementation challenges like, Lack of Clarity on GST Provisions (Rules and Regulation), Increase number of returns, **IT Infrastructure, Lack of skilled resources, Challenges to legislation, Dual administration, Multiple registration, Extensive Training to Tax Administration Staff** etc. if we overcome the above said implementation challenges, and implemented correctly, can do wonders for India's economy. Along with eliminating double taxation and lowering product price, the GST can also assimilate

the informal sector into the greater Indian economy and provide a much needed boost for India's flagging export market.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The major objectives of this study are as follows:-

1. To know the challenges in implementation of GST in India
2. To know the impact of GST on Agriculture sector.

METHODOLOGY:

Data used in the study are secondary in nature and mostly collected from online journals. The study covers a period from 2017 July 1 to till now.

Challenges in implementation of GST:

The following are the some of the biggest challenges in implementation of GST in India.

Goods and Service Tax Structure: The GST was originally designed to simplify the entire tax structure and therefore a single rate of tax was suggested. In the world most of countries have kept just one slab of GST but in Indian contest, there is 0 % slab, 5% slab, 12% slab, 18% slab and 28 % slab. In addition a new slab of 3 % has been introduced specifically for gold. These multiple slabs are going to be a change in actual implementation

Multiple registrations: As per model GST law every service provider has to obtain registration in each state where services are being provided against centralized registration scheme under the existing law. Given the complexities of some of industries, separate registration in each states where they operate will result into tremendous task to comply with law.

Increase in the number of returns: Business will need to file 37 returns in a year (three returns per month and one annual return) per state," the Economic Times

reported on June 5, 2017. "If it does business from offices in more than one state, the number of returns will go up accordingly. A business with offices in three states will have to file 111 tax returns in a year."

Type Of Returns To Be Filed Under Goods & Services Tax			
RETURN FORM	WHAT TO FILE?	BY WHOM?	BY WHEN?
GSTR-1	Details of outward supplies of taxable goods and/or services effected	Registered Taxable Supplier	10th of the next month
GSTR-2	Details of inward supplies of taxable goods and/or services effected claiming input tax credit.	Registered Taxable Recipient	15th of the next month
GSTR-3	Monthly return on the basis of finalization of details of outward supplies and inward supplies along with the payment of amount of tax.	Registered Taxable Person	20th of the next month
GSTR-4	Quarterly return for compounding taxable person.	Composition Supplier	18th of the month succeeding quarter
GSTR-5	Return for Non-Resident foreign taxable person	Non-Resident Taxable Person	20th of the next month
GSTR-6	Return for Input Service Distributor	Input Service Distributor	13th of the next month
GSTR-7	Return for authorities deducting tax at source.	Tax Deductor	10th of the next month

GSTR-8	Details of supplies effected through e-commerce operator and the amount of tax collected	E-commerce Operator/Tax Collector	10th of the next month
GSTR-9	Annual Return	Registered Taxable Person	31st December of next financial year
GSTR-10	Final Return	Taxable person whose registration has been surrendered or cancelled.	Within three months of the date of cancellation or date of cancellation order, whichever is later.
GSTR-11	Details of inward supplies to be furnished by a person having UIN	Person having UIN and claiming refund	28th of the month following the month for which statement is filed

Source: K Raghu & Co

Input Tax Credit: One of the key features of GST is the seamless input tax credit that will be available under the GST system but the seamless credit has a lot of assumptions. For example, many products like petrol, diesel and alcohol have been kept out of the purview of GST. Integrating tax credits across the products will be a nightmare as equivalent audit trail may not be available for all transactions.

Anti-Profitteering Clause: The Anti-Profitteering clause in the GST bill could again lead to another practical challenge. Under this clause, the business is required pass any tax cuts to the customer in entirety. While this will not be an issue in case of service invoicing, it could be an issue in case of products where the maximum retail price (MRP) includes many items apart from GST. Delineating the impact of GST from these set of factors may be practically difficult and may open the doors to endless litigation.

Upgrade IT infrastructure: The process of tracking interstate transactions will be extremely complex and will require an infallible IT system. Now, six million micros, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs) are to be upgrade their IT technology according to the new provisions of GST. Upgrade IT infrastructure involves huge capital and proper training to employees in the organization. Tax and accounting professionals jointly need to ensure that their clients' current systems are compatible with their GST Service Provider (GSP).

Lack of skilled resources: GST subject knowledge staff is required to effectively implementation of New GST provisions. This is creating an additional workload to employees to upgrade the knowledge about the New provisions of the GST. GST is both a challenge and an opportunity for tax and accounting professionals.

Lack of Clarity on GST Rules and Regulation: Various rules and regulations of GST are still not clear. Categorization of goods and services in various cases is still unclear. Provisions for anti-profiteering, as well as the now-deferred e-way bill, which tracks consignments across states, are unclear. The new tax regime requires transporters to generate e-way bills on the GST portals which include incurring substantial costs to install radio frequency identification devices (RFIDs). Currently there is no clarity on who will bear the bill for the infrastructure.

Extensive Training to Tax Administration Staff: GST is absolutely different from existing system. It, therefore, requires that tax administration staff at both Centre and state to be trained properly in terms of concept, legislation and Procedure.

Impact of GST on Agriculture sector: Agricultural sector is considered the backbone of Indian economy but due to implementation of GST this backbone is broken and is suffering a lot as tax slabs in agro sector has been increased without taking initiatives for making the infrastructure and new irrigation techniques for the betterment of farmers but imposing more tax than before

not only lays adverse effects on agricultural sector but is also responsible for the increase in price in manufacturing sector too, as cost of production will increase if the primary or raw material is costly. We can show the adverse effects on agro sector by following table:

S.No	Particulars	Tax rate Before GST	Tax rate After GST
01	Fertilizers	6% (1%excise + 5% VAT)	12%.
02	Milk products	Vat 2%	Fresh Milk- Nil Skimmed milk -5% Condensed Milk-18 %
03	Tea	4-5 %	5 %

CONCLUSION

India is facing some of the GST implementation challenges like, Lack of Clarity on GST Provisions (Rules and Regulation), Increase number of returns, **IT Infrastructure**, Lack of skilled resources, **Challenges to legislation, Dual administration, Multiple registration, Extensive Training to Tax Administration Staff** etc. if we overcome the above said implementation challenges, and implemented correctly, can do wonders for India's economy. Along with eliminating double taxation and lowering product price, the GST can also assimilate the informal sector into the greater Indian economy and provide a much needed boost for India's flagging export market.

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